

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure 1 – SETDB1 regulates ERV silencing in naive ESCs.

a. Deep amplicon sequencing from oxBS-treated DNA was used to measure 5hmC levels at ERVs in primed and naive ESCs; each data point represents the average value from two biological replicates at a given CpG within the amplicon (ANOVA with Tukey's multiple comparison test, * $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$, **** $p < 0.0001$). **b.** RT-qPCR data of primed and naive ESCs. Each bar represents mean values and error bars indicate s.d. ($n = 3-10$; t-test, * $p < 0.05$). **c.** Western blot (representative data from $n = 2$) and RT-qPCR analyses ($n = 7$) show SETDB1 depletion by lentiviral delivery of shRNAs (ANOVA with Tukey's multiple comparison test, *** $p < 0.001$, **** $p < 0.0001$). **d.** RT-qPCR data of KAP1 depleted ESCs at IAPs in primed and naive conditions.

Supplementary Figure 2 – Removal of TET2 dampens SETDB1-mediated IAP activation in naïve cells. **a.** *Tet2* KO ESC targeting strategy. A 12.7kb genomic region containing *Tet2* exons 11 to 14 is depicted. *Tet2* exon 14 was substituted by a loxP-PGK-Neo-p(A)-loxP cassette by homologous recombination and then deleted by Cre-mediated recombination. EcoRI digestion fragments were used for Southern blot analysis using the 5' and 3' probes depicted. **b.** Southern blot analysis using the 3' probe shows correct targeting of *Tet2* locus. Northern blot analysis using a probe for exon 14 is unable to detect RNA in three independent *Tet2* KO ES clones. **c.** Relative expression of IAPs in *Tet2*-depleted *Tet1* KO ESCs or, reciprocally, in *Tet1*-depleted *Tet2* KO ESC, in 2i conditions. The error bars indicate s.d. from three technical replicates. **d.** Western blot reveals similar level of TET2 expression in the *Tet2* rescue lines (representative replicate of n=2). Global 5hmC levels reveals similar levels between WT *Tet2* ESCs and cells rescued with WT TET2, whereas TET2 KO ESCs and cells rescued with the mutant TET2 has low levels of 5hmC. **e.** RT-qPCR analysis of *Tet2* WT, KO and rescue cell lines at IAPs in primed ESCs (n=3-4; ANOVA with Tukey's multiple comparison test, * p<0.05, *** p<0.001, **** p<0.0001). The results are presented as the ratio of shSETDB1/shScr and mean \pm s.d.

Supplementary Figure 3 – SETDB1-mediated IAP activation is not linked to DNA methylation changes. **a-c.** 5hmC levels in primed and naïve conditions upon SETDB1 knockdown (a), 5mC+5hmC levels in naïve ESCs upon KAP1 knockdown (b), 5mC levels in primed ESCs upon SETDB1 knockdown (c) at IAPs; each data point represents the average value from two biological replicates at a given CpG within the amplicon (ANOVA with Tukey’s multiple comparison test, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, **** $p < 0.0001$). **d.** H3K9me3, TET1 and TET2 enrichment across individual IAP copies in primed ESCs compared to pool of IAP copies (blue bars). **e.** 5mC+5hmC levels upon SETDB1 removal at individual IAPs in primed and naïve conditions ($n=2$).

Supplementary Figure 4 – SETDB1-depletion does not lead to DNA methylation changes. **a.** 5mC+5hmC levels in naïve ESCs upon SETDB1 knockdown with and without vitamin C at IAPs; each data point represents the average value from two biological replicates at a given CpG within the amplicon (ANOVA with Tukey’s multiple comparison test, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, **** $p < 0.0001$). **b.** RT-qPCR data of SETDB1 depleted ESCs at IAPs in naïve conditions with and without vitamin C. **c.** 5mC+5hmC levels upon SETDB1 removal at IAP pools and individual IAP copies in *Tet2* KD naïve cells ($n=1$); each data point represents the value at a given CpG within the amplicon (ANOVA with Tukey’s multiple comparison test).

Supplementary Figure 5 – TET2 activity is associated with loss of H4R3me2 at IAPs. **a.** ChIP-qPCR data for H3K27me3 at IAPs upon SETDB1 loss in the presence and absence of TET2 (n=2-3). **b.** Repeat classes that are enriched for H4R3me2s in naïve ESCs. IAP elements are indicated in red **c.** Relative expression of transposons in Tet2 rescue cell lines based on RNA-seq data (n=3, * p<0.05) **d.** RNA-seq data of Prmt5, Prmt7 and Jmjd6 genes in Tet2 rescue lines upon SETDB1 depletion.